

CHAPTER 1

PROBLEM STATEMENT AND REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter included the introduction, theoretical framework, statement of the problem, hypothesis, scope and limitation, significance of the study, definition of terms, and review of related literature.

Introduction

Travelling by sea is one of the common modes of transporting or going from one place to another, while many finds it enjoyable and fun, unfortunately there are numerous problems that can be faced by passengers in the sea faring industry. Some of the problems encountered includes limited vehicle parking space, limited passenger waiting rooms, shortage of manpower, lack of space contributing to port congestion, and shortage of other facilities needed to improve their operational performance.

The Port of San Jose; located in the Province of Dinagat Islands, plays an important role in connecting the province to the mainland, this port is felt more and more important and strategic because it provides an enormous impact on the growth and development in this province because it serves as the entry and exit of goods and staples. Being an island province; the port also serves as the only travel option because of the geographic location of the province, so the people have to

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experience traversing the seas in order to reach the mainland. In this regard this Research study entitled "**Problems encountered by the Passengers in Port of San Jose Dinagat Islands**" aims to assess and determine what are the problems faced by the passengers and to formulate action plan to minimize if not solve the problems.

In this regard, House Bill No. 6225 dated November 21, 2022 was introduced by Representative Rufus B. Rodriguez. This bill states that when Republic Act 9993 or the Coast Guard Law was enacted in 2009, the Philippine Coast Guard was among others, vested with the necessary authority and responsibility to perform preventive measures in ensuring the safety of merchant vessels. The was passed to strengthen the PCG's authority to meet new challenges. *(Reli, 2023.)*

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

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This study is anchored in Grounded theory, a well-known methodology employed in many research studies. Qualitative and quantitative data generation techniques can be used in a grounded theory study. Grounded theory attempts to uncover the meanings of people's social actions, interactions and experiences. These explanations are called 'grounded' because they are grounded in the participants' own explanations or interpretations.

Barney Glaser and Anselm Strauss originated this method in their 1967 book, *The Discovery Of Grounded Theory*. The grounded theory approach has been used by researchers in various disciplines, including sociology, anthropology, psychology, economics and public health. With Grounded theory the researchers can identify the problems encountered by the passengers in San Jose Port by understanding passenger's actions, interactions, and experience, then the researchers can formulate or develop an action plan to improve a port passenger experience.

INPUT

1. Demographic profile of the respondents:
1.1. Age
1.2. Sex
1.3. Civil Status

PROCESS

1. Identify the Demographic profile of the respondents in as to:
1.1. Age
1.2. Sex
1.3. Civil Status

OUTPUT

Figure 1. Schematic Model of the Study

Statement of the Problem

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The main problem of this study is to identify the problems encountered by passengers in San Jose Port.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions.

1. What is the Demographic profile of the respondents as to:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Civil status
 - 1.4 Educational Attainment
 - 1.5 Family Monthly Income
 - 1.6 Purpose
2. What are the problems encountered by the passengers in San Jose Port, Located in Dinagat Islands in terms of:
 - 2.2 Hospitality/ Quality of service
 - 2.2 Security
 - 2.3 Facilities
3. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile of respondents and the problems encountered by the passengers in San Jose Port, Located in Dinagat Islands.

Hypothesis

Problem no. 1 and 2 were hypothesis-free while problem 3 was hypothesized as follows:

H₀₁. There is no statistically significant relationship between the demographic profile and the challenges encountered by the Philippine Port Authority Personnel on their operation in San Jose, Dinagat Islands

Significance of the Study

PPA Personnel - The findings of this study will guide and tighten their strategies in management that would help for the challenges encountered by the Philippine Port Authority Personnel on their operation in San Jose, Dinagat Islands.

Passenger - This study would make them know and aware about the preparation for the Philippine Port Authority personnel in their operation.

Future researchers - The collected data will serve as a base for future research pertaining to this current issue.

Scope and Limitation- The scope of this study was limited in terms of focus, respondents, and setting.

Focus. This study aims to determine the challenges encountered by the (Philippine Port Authority) PPA personnel on their operation in San Jose, Dinagat Islands Port.

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Respondents. This study will be conducted on PPA Personnel of San Jose Dinagat Islands.

Setting. This study will be conducted in the office of Philippine Ports Authority (PPA) in the Municipality of San Jose, Dinagat Islands.

Definition of the terms

Cargos - it is the goods carried on a vessel, and also it can be illegal or legal.

Contraband - refers to the terms that are illegal to trade, carry and produce, and also that are illegal to import or export are attempt to be smuggled into a country.

Government Strategy - identify key strategic risks and critical issues for agency to achieve its vision and purpose.

Machine detector - this is used by the PPA personnel to detect the illegal contraband such as drugs, weapons, and others.

PPA - is the primary movement agency concerned with the planning and development of the country's seaports. It also managing the port to achieve passenger and community safety.

Transportation - is the movement of goods and person from place to place and the various means by which such movement is accomplished.

Technology - is the application of knowledge for the achieving practical goals in the port and also a products resulting from such efforts.

Review of Related Literature

This chapter presents foreign and local literature which are relevant to the present undertaking. Literature cited enables the researcher to have a better understanding and wider perspective of this study.

Foreign Literature & Studies

According to **GN Kenyon, 2018** Improving the return on investment in ports: opportunities in data management. Ports provide a critical link in the supply chain by connecting sea, air, and land transport. They provide facilities and services for the transfer, storage, inspection, and control of the goods moving both in and out of a country. Inefficient port management can increase costs considerably and hamper the timeliness of delivery. Many traditional industry techniques fail to capitalize on the global nature of data, thereby omitting the maximum benefit available.

The study of **Dogukan Aksu, 2018** of detecting port scan attempts with comparative analysis of deep learning and support vector machine algorithms, International congress on big data, deep learning and fighting cyber terrorism (IBIGDELFT), 77-80, 2018 Compared to the past, developments in computer and

communication technologies have provided extensive and advanced changes. The usage of new technologies provide great benefits to individuals, companies, and governments, however, it causes some problems against them. For example, the privacy of important information, security of stored data platforms, availability of knowledge etc.

Written by **Richard Alphonse Biramata 2014**, the Open University of Tanzania, This descriptive study examined the challenges of compliance to Public Procurement Act 2011 to Tanzania procurement entities. Specific objectives included to investigate the reasons of non-compliance to PPA 2011 internal and external to the Tanzania Procurement Entities, to analyzing the challenges of procedures and guidelines of PPA 2011 to the whole procurement system and to establish the extent to which the implementation of the PPA 2011 affects the performance of public entities in Tanzania. The study was conducted in TPA and used both quantitative and qualitative research approach to the case study. This study used data collection methods, with a selected TPA, PPRA and PSPTB and involved thirty eight respondents.

Furthermore **Marcello Risitano 2017**, Strategic monitoring of port authorities activities: Proposal of a multi-dimensional digital dashboard. The consequence of port evolution is that port authorities (PA) around the world are modifying their nature and their role, acquiring more and more an active role

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in the governance of logistic systems and are often adopting managerial and entrepreneurial behaviors. This new role of PA requires the adoption of a complex approach to monitoring the performance of the single stakeholders and of the whole port. Existing studies on port performance consider only specific indicators of port performance such as operational and financial efficiency neglecting aspects like customer satisfaction, port security and port sustainability

Also **Santiago Herrera & Gaobo PangEcomod, 2016**. Recent policy debates on pro-growth policies have emphasized the potential role of public expenditure in infrastructure. The degree to which growth actually responds in a sustainable fashion depends on the efficiency with which capital is used. The object of this paper is to gauge efficiency in container ports. Based on non-parametric methods, the paper estimates the maximum attainable output for a given input level and gauges efficiency as the distance from the observed input-output combinations to this frontier.

The study of **VF Valentine, 2011** 8th National Maritime Conference and Exhibition a comparison of African port performance. Stakeholders and port users alike are concerned with the concept of port performance despite the absence of a universally accepted formula for its measurement. Understanding performance is a concept fundamental to any business, whether it is the measuring of achievements against set goals and objectives or, against the competition. Ports are no exception

and it is only by comparison with other ports that performance can be evaluated. There are many factors that have an effect upon the performance of a port; the location, infrastructure, superstructure and connectivity to other ports are but a few. Over the last twenty years much reorganization has occurred within ports following the global adoption of privatization policies by individual governments.

Written by **Umur Bucak, İbrahim Mücdat Başaran, Soner Esmer & Journal, 2020** dimensions of the port performance: a review of literature. The port performance has frequently been studied in the academic literature, and the first studies on the subject are focused on financial or operational dimensions. However, today, port performance has become multi-dimensional due to the changing roles of the ports to its stakeholders, and the fact that local competition has been replaced by global competition through continuously developing routes, etc. Within this study, it is aimed to determine each dimension of the port performance concept which had been handled as a multi-dimensional process in recent years in literature. For this purpose, port performance literature is reviewed and frequency analysis of the related studies was made.

Furthermore **Salama Benazar Rosana, 2013** a socio-economic & environmental impact of the port efficiency in the transport logistic chain. Port efficiency and productivity are two of the most important factors in defining the competitiveness of a port. Lately it has been shown that while the ports are more

developed and more competitive, have a greater tendency to respecting the environment, because that same competitiveness, are encouraged to apply at their facilities to international quality standards such as ISO14000, including measures that represent respect for the environment and corporate policies designed for that purpose.

Aslo **José Humberto Ablanedo-Rosas, Hongman Gao, Xiaochuan Zheng, Bahram Alidaee, Haibo Wang, 2010**. This research examines the relative efficiency of 11 major Chinese ports by using an innovative adopted version of Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). DEA is a non-parametric approach to weigh the inputs/outputs and measure the relative efficiency of decision-making units. This paper adopts an output-oriented version of DEA based on financial ratios in which no inputs are utilized. The new adopted DEA model provides a rounded judgement on port efficiency taking into consideration multiple financial ratios simultaneously and combining them into a single measure of efficiency. The mathematical model is solved for every port, and the relative efficiency of each port is determined. The results of DEA show that the higher a port's efficiency ratio in relation to the corresponding ratio of another port, the higher the efficiency of this port. Finally, suggestions based on the data analysis are provided for managerial decision makers to improve the areas needed for port operating efficiency.

In addition **George K Vaggelas, 2019**, Measurement of port performance from users' perspective Going beyond the usual approach of measuring port performance-focusing on the efficiency of port operations-this paper aims to look into shipping lines and other port users' perceptions on port performance.

Local Literature and Studies

According to **Kris A Francisco, Valerie L Lim, 2021**, the Government strategies in the water transport sector: A closer look at Philippine ports. Transport infrastructure is one of the key elements in achieving a balanced growth within an economy. The water transport sector, in particular, plays a much larger role in an archipelagic country such as the Philippines. The country however, has underinvested in public infrastructure for several years which resulted to low quality of infrastructure and some inefficiency in the operation of seaports, which are the main infrastructure in the water transport sector. This study analyzed the performance of the Philippine ports through domestic and international lenses by utilizing previous studies and comparative statistics on ASEAN countries. Results show that despite having more international ports, our container and cargo throughput as well as international passenger traffic is lower compared to our ASEAN neighbors. This can be attributed to the perceived low quality of our ports and low level of shipping connectivity. Review of

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previous studies reveal that issues in the water transport sector are related to quality of infrastructure, inefficiencies in operation and congestion.

Furthermore **Suzie M Huelgas, Victor A Arellano, 2021**, Green transformational leadership, green human resource management and green innovation: Key to environmental performance of selected port management offices of Philippine. Anthropogenic factors are undoubtedly causing damages to the world's natural resources and disruption to the ecosystem services. As an offshoot of government interventions, sustainable development principle was placed at the core of every development undertaking. This heightened environmental awareness created huge impact to government organizations as pro-environmental behaviors become a prevalent norm. Apparently, Government-Owned and Controlled Corporations (GOCC) in the Philippines have also been implementing programs that are inclined towards environmental protection. This study examined pro environmental behavior in the leadership, human resource management and innovations in selected Port Management Offices (PMOs) of Philippine Ports Authority (PPA), and its effects on the organization's environmental performance. It particularly assessed the observance of Green Transformational Leadership (GTL), Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices, Green Innovation (GI) and its impacts on their Environmental Performance (EP). This study used explanatory sequential mixed

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method which draws on the strength of both qualitative and quantitative research.

Also **Chato May J Villanueva, Cel-Anne T Firme, Mark Gerald V Manalo, Kathlyn V Montalbo, Vladimir Von M Suico, Gloria M Regalario, Lourdes P Panaligan, Annalie D Pateña, 2015,** Preventive Measures Adapted by One of the Philippine Government Agency in Port Operation. This study primarily aims to evaluate the preventive measures adapted by Bureau of Customs Port of Batangas. The objectives of this study were to assess the level of effectiveness of the preventive measures adapted; identify the problems encountered in the implementation of the preventive measure; to test the significant relationship between the level of effectiveness and problems encountered as perceived by the two groups of respondents; and to propose plan of action that may be designed to address the level of effectiveness of the preventive measures adapted. The present study was a descriptive research that used quantitative analysis. The respondents of the study were the heads and employees from the four division of Bureau of Customs, Port of Batangas such as Assessment Division, Port Operation Division, Customs Police Division-Enforcement and Security Service (CPD-ESS) and Customs Intelligence and Investigation Service (CIIS). The results revealed that the preventive measures adapted by Bureau of Customs were assessed by the respondents as very effective. However, two of the preventive measures were

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assessed by the two groups of respondents such as heads and employees as effective only. The researchers recommended that Bureau of Customs, Port of Batangas continuously strengthen their implementation of their preventive measures for further prevention and suppression of smuggling.

Written by **Ivan Kaye F Bantigue, 2023**, Assessment of the contribution of the Port of Manila to the economic development of the Philippines from 1910 to 2010. A country's seaports are active participants in the trade and commerce of a nation. Through the seaport's piers, people and goods pass through and contribute to the Philippines' economic development. Undoubtedly, the Port of Manila significantly contributes to the Philippine economy. This research attempts to discuss the history of Port of Manila from the American period to the first decade of the 21st century. It discusses the development of the port, its challenges and problems, and its role in Philippine economic history. The sources from this research are official and commercial reports and anecdotes from the people who lived during this study period.

In the study of **Banuelos, 2022**, Digitization was a high priority for the Philippine Ports Authority. It was recently concluded that digitization was really a high priority now at PPA to prevent occurrence of usual problems encountered by the people at the port. It also emphasize the importance of expanding the agency's communication.

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Philippine Ports Authority (2017) have mentioned that throughout the years, there are various challenges that they have encountered. Some of those challenges are regarding in pushing the reset button to align its processes and policies to the trends that are still parallel to the overall dream of the country. However, the modernization and development of the ports were all visible year 2017 onwards. With the partnership made with different agencies, every plans and works and even challenges were evaluated and given desirable solutions.

In the statement of **PPA General Manager Daniel R. Santiago (2020)** a news was released by the Philippine Port Authority stating that Manila Ports fear to shut down due to continued cargo congestion., the port can be shut down if the owners of these cargos and consignees continue to shun calls to withdraw cleared, ready to delivery and overstayed cargos. The Manila International Container terminal also cleared that these overstayng cargos are one of the hindrance why there are not enough breathing space for Manila port terminals to operate efficiently and productively.

Gilberto M Llanto, 2016 Philippine infrastructure and connectivity: challenges and reforms. The Philippines has performed creditably well in the past few years. Ensuring better infrastructure and connectivity is crucial in attaining inclusive growth. This will require substantial investments in infrastructure. Various reforms to address the infrastructure

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lack were implemented but there is scope for more reforms: improving fiscal space, reforming budgetary processes, improving public-private partnerships (PPPs) and the regulatory environment, and better policy coordination to address problems of connectivity and infrastructure. The Philippines has to continuously improve the governance framework, ensure stability and predictability of policies and regulations. Better coordination among a diverse set of governmental infrastructure bodies, and also between government and the private sector is needed to address infrastructure bottlenecks.

Also **Riches Bacero, C Tan, 2013** Strategic port improvements and maximization of the benefits of RoRo Shipping Services in Southwestern Mindanao. The primary goal of this study is to examine the improvement of shipping services and related reduction of transport cost in Southwestern Mindanao resulting from RoRo shipping operation. The improvement of ports and the existence of RoRo shipping in Southwestern Mindanao provide great help in the transportation and movement of goods and people in Basilan, Sulu, and Tawi-Tawi. The construction of a RoRo facility in the Port of Lamitan resulted in modal shift from Non-RoRo to RoRo shipping.

In addition **L Arivalagan, R Rengarajan, 2012** ADEQUACY AND EFFECTIVENESS OF THE LOGISTICS INDUSTRY IN NORTH INDIA-IMPLICATION FOR EXPORT PERFORMANCE. The Port of Manila, the largest seaport in the country, has been recognized as the most

widely used port in the Greater Capital Region with utilization rate of 71.6% compared to only 2.3% and 6.1% utilization of Batangas and Subic Ports, respectively (NEDA, 2012). The ports of Batangas and Subic were developed in order to accommodate excess traffic in the port of Manila and promote growth and development in CALABARZON and Central Luzon. This leads to the congestion of Manila Port and the underutilization of the other two ports in the Greater Capital Region. The situation was intensified during the implementation of the recently lifted Manila truck ban. The study recognizes that issues and problems still persist in the logistics sector even after the regulation was put off.

CHAPTER 2

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter presented the research design, research setting, research respondents, data gathering procedure, research instrument, validity and reliability, ethical

consideration, and statistical treatment of data that will use in gathering data.

Research Design

This study will use the descriptive design where in the researchers will gather quantitative information that will be used for statistical in reference to the target respondents Philippine port authority personnel through data analysis. The researchers will provide survey questionnaire containing for the respondents. The design help the researchers define and measure the significance to determine their Challenges encountered by the Passenger in Port of SanJose, Dinagat Islands.

Research Setting

This study will be conducted at Port of San Jose, Dinagat Islands. This research setting has chosen for reason. First, our respondent is located in our chosen location. Second, the result of this study can be beneficial for the improvement of

both the passengers and PPA, which will also benefit to everyone within it including the researchers. The location of the Research setting can be seen in figure 2.

Figure 2 below shows them a of San Jose PPA which is located at Puro`k-1. Barangay Poblacion, SanJose, Dinagat Islands.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study are selected individual from the six (6) vessel in the port of San Jose, Dinagat island. The number of respondents is the sample size extracted from the passenger of every vessel in municipality of San Jose, port authority. The 306 samples were allocated to the six (6) vessel included in the study.

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The following vessels has the authorized capacity of passengers, News MPC 3 (300), News MPC 4(300), Vince Gabriel (192), Reiseschatz (130), Vienl's Liner 1 (188) and Viel's Liner 2 (188). Table 1 distribution of the respondents. It can be seen that there is a total passenger of the vessel of 660 in the port of San Jose, Dinagat island.

The Formula:

$$N = \frac{N}{(1 + Ne^2)}$$

Whereas: n= no. of sample is 306

N= total capacity of passenger 1,298

Error Margin/ margin of error is 0.05

Slovin's Formula:

$$N = \frac{1,298}{(1 + 1,298(0.05)^2)}$$

$$\frac{1,298}{(1 + 3.245)}$$

$$\frac{1,298}{4.245}$$

n=

306 samples

VESSEL	PASSENGER CAPACITY	SAMPLE SITE
News MPC 3	300	54
News MPC 4	300	52
Vince Gabriel	192	51
Reiseschatz	130	49
Viel's Liner 1	188	50
Viel's Liner 2	188	50
Total	1,298	306

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents

The 306 respondents were obtained by using Slovin's formula with the total number of capacity of passenger in every vessels.

Data Gathering Procedures

Upon the approval of the research committee the researchers will then secure a letter of request to the persons involve. From the School Vice-President, to Vice-President of Academic Affairs, down to the PPA Personnel to grant the researchers to

conduct the study. Once approved, the researchers will then coordinate to the Philippine Port Authority Personnel

Respondents to conduct the survey and distribute the questionnaire. The question considering their strategy. After that, the questionnaire will be collected and data will be analyzed.

Research Instrument

The researchers will create instrument about the strategy on handling operation in the port.

The questionnaire and checklist will be validated for its reliability then it will be distributed to the PPA personnel to gather data and measure their strategy methods and operation in the port. The questionnaire will compose two parts, Part I will be the respondents profile in terms of their age, sex, civil status and Highest Educational attainment. Part II will contain 15 items pertaining to the PPA Personnel management and control system.

Validity

In order to achieve the instrument's content validity and reliability, the researchers will present the chosen research tool to the panel members and research committee for review, corrections and suggestions and it will be reflected on the drafted administer the official data gathering procedure.

Ethical Consideration

The researchers assured ethical considerations in conducting the study. First, the researchers provided a letter seeking approval from the research instructor to submit to the PPA of San Jose, Dinagat Island for the conduct of the study. The passengers become the respondents and participate in conducting the survey. The said respondents were given consent letter by the researchers in order for them to be fully informed about the said study then researchers provide sufficient information to the respondents for them to understand clearly the implication of their participation, their ideas and opinions are highly accepted and it will be protect by the researchers.

Statistical Treatment of Data.

To analyze the data gathered in the study, the following statistical tools were used.

Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution.

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These tools were used to determine the profile of respondents in terms of their age, sex, civil status, Highest Educational attainment, family monthly income, and purpose.

Mean and **standard Deviation**, will used in the study to compute the results of PPA personnel in their operation against contraband.

One-Way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance). This tool was utilized to analyze the significant relationship between the Challenges encountered by the PPA Personnel on their operation in San Jose, Dinagat Islands port.

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**Problems Encountered by the Passengers in Port of San Jose
Dinagat Islands**

Part 1 - Profile of the respondents

DIRECTION: Please check (✓) the box that corresponds to your profile

Name: _____ (optional)

A. Age: _____

B. Sex: Male Female

C. Civil Status:

Single Married
 Widowed Separated

D. Educational Attainment

<input type="checkbox"/> Elementary Level	<input type="checkbox"/> High School Graduate
<input type="checkbox"/> Elementary Graduate	<input type="checkbox"/> College Level
<input type="checkbox"/> High School Level	<input type="checkbox"/> College Graduate
<input type="checkbox"/> Master's Degree	<input type="checkbox"/> Doctorate Degree

E. Family Monthly Income

<input type="checkbox"/> Below 5,000	<input type="checkbox"/> 5,001-10,000
<input type="checkbox"/> 10,001-15,000	<input type="checkbox"/> 15,001-20,000
<input type="checkbox"/> 20,001-25,000	<input type="checkbox"/> .. 25,001-30,000
<input type="checkbox"/> 30,001-35,000	<input type="checkbox"/> .. 35,001-40,000
<input type="checkbox"/> 40,001-45,000	<input type="checkbox"/> .. 45,001-Above

F. Purpose

<input type="checkbox"/> Business/Purchase	<input type="checkbox"/> Studies/Schooling
<input type="checkbox"/> Touring/Exploring	<input type="checkbox"/> Appointments/Seminars
<input type="checkbox"/> Other Purpose: _____	

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Part 2 - Problems encountered by the passengers in Port of San Jose Dinagat Island.

DIRECTION: Please rate the following statements according to the scale given below based on your perspective.

INTERPRETATION	SCALE
Strongly Agree	4
Agree	3
Disagree	2
Strongly Disagree	1

Statements/Indicator

Indicators	SA	A	D	SD
	4	3	2	1
A. Hospitality/ Quality of service				
1. Port personnel's are well-mannered towards the passenger.				
2. Travel personnel performs their duty efficiently.				
3. Vessel crews and captains shows positive response to passengers.				
4. Port Personnel maintains "safety first" policy				
5. Port Personnel maintains professionalism & Ethical Standards.				
B. Security				
1. Security personnel inspects bags, luggage, and others.				
2. Port Security Personnel are well mannered when dealing with passengers.				
3. The Cost Guard will check the authorized capacity/number of passengers per MARINA.				
4. Adequate/accessible life jackets for the passengers, and vessel crews.				
5. Port Security has screening devices such as metal detectors and other security devices.				

C. Facilities				
1. There are enough comfort rooms in San Jose Port.				
2. Comfort rooms, waiting rooms and other facilities are regularly cleaned and sanitized.				
3. There are Emergency/medical cabinet readily available if there is emergency.				
4. San Jose Port has Information desks or Bulletin boards to keep passengers aware/informed.				
5. Waiting area has enough space to accommodate passengers.				

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